

Potentiometric Studies of CdCl₂ solutions in 20 percent Dioxane-Water Mixture at 35°, 40° and 45°.

S. C. MOHANTY, U. C. MISHRA, K. C. SINGH and P. K. DAS

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-3

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Dissociation constant of CdCl⁺ ⇌ Cd⁺⁺ + Cl⁻ have been determined at 35°, 40° and 45° by using the cell of the type :

and found to be 0.0079, 0.00767 and 0.0074 respectively. The ΔH of ionisation of CdCl⁺ ⇌ Cd⁺⁺ + Cl⁻ is found to be 1300.00 Calories ± 100 Cal/mole. Using the ionisation constant of CdCl⁺ and studying the cell :

and HgCd (11.8%)|CdCl₂ (m₁)|AgCl|Ag|AgCl|CdCl₂ (m₂)|Cd (11.8%)Hg in 20% dioxane-water mixture, E₀ for the cell II is found to be 0.5305, 0.5262 and 0.5205 at 35°, 40° and 45° respectively.

VARIOUS workers¹⁻⁵ have reported the existence of the species CdCl⁺ from their studies in aqueous solutions of cadmium chloride. Little work has been done to study the behaviour of cadmium chloride in solution of water-dioxane mixture containing 20% of dioxane as solvent. In the present investigation the cell :

was studied to obtain accurately the ionisation constant of CdCl⁺ ⇌ Cd⁺⁺ + Cl⁻ assuming the first stage of dissociation of CdCl₂ ⇌ CdCl⁺ + Cl⁻ to be complete. In order to determine the E₀ of Hg, Cd (11.8%) Cd⁺⁺, the following cells were studied at 35°, 40° and 45°.

Experimental

Dioxane used was B.D.H. 'Analar' quality, which was purified by refluxing with sodium hydroxide for 45 hr, the distilled sample treated with sodium wire and was finally distilled just before use. Hydrochloric acid used was a Kahlbaum sample, which was diluted to the desired strength with triple distilled water and the resulting solution was distilled, so that the middle fraction of a constant boiling mixture was collected. The chloride content of this solution was analysed gravimetrically by the usual method⁶.

E. Merck 'extra pure' sample of cadmium chloride was twice crystallised from water and the crystals were filtered in a glass cintered crucible, washed and kept in a desiccator. A stock solution of cadmium chloride in triple distilled water was prepared and was analysed for its cadmium and chloride contents by usual methods⁷. This stock solution was used to make the solutions of different molalities with freshly distilled dioxane and air free triple distilled water to make the solution to contain 20% dioxane. The hydrochloric acid solution was similarly prepared. All solutions were prepared in the molal scale.

A thermal electrolytic Ag-AgCl electrode was used as has been reported by Harned and Ehlers⁸. Hydrogen was prepared by electrolysis baryta solution and the evolved hydrogen made oxygen free by passing the gas through copper gauze heated to 500°. Then the oxygen free hydrogen was led through a series of bubblers containing the experimental solution and subsequently to the cell in the thermostat through another two washers. Platinised platinum electrode was prepared and other precautions were taken regarding the use of the hydrogen electrode as recommended by Ives and Janz⁹. Connections to the Ag, AgCl half element was made by fitting the lead tubes with vacuum stopcocks with the same bore as the tubes and subsequently through vacuum tested standard glass joints. The entire assembly of the apparatus was in glass and use of rubber was scrupulously avoided. The apparatus assembly was vacuum tested, closing the hydrogen out-let so that no leak was observed and thereby aerial contamination was excluded. Cadmium amalgam consisting 11.8% of cadmium was prepared in oxygen free nitrogen atmosphere by using triple

distilled mercury and cadmium metal of E. Merk 'extra pure' sample. Care was taken to see that either during the preparation, transfer of the solution to the electrode vessels or the electrode assembly do not come in contact with air by suitable manipulation and using oxygen free nitrogen.

An air thermostat was used in which the temperature was regulated within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. A Pye potentiometer was taken and the e.m.f. can be read with an accuracy of ± 0.1 mv. Duplicate experiments were performed in each case and the duplicates generally agreed within 0.2 mv. However, the difference went up to 0.4 mv in some cases. The e.m.f. readings were corrected to atmospheric pressure using the vapour pressure data of Havorka, Schaefer and Dreisbach¹⁰ and the reported e.m.f. values are the mean of the corrected e.m.f. readings.

Discussion

The e.m.f. of the cell (I) is given by :

$$E = E_0 - \frac{RT}{F} \cdot \ln [H^+][Cl^-]\gamma_{H^+} \gamma_{Cl^-}$$

The activity co-efficient γ in terms of molalities can be converted to the rational activity co-efficients f^+ & f^- so that making use of the Debye-Hückel-Brönstead expression it can be expressed as :

$$-\log f_{4+} f_{Cl^-} = \frac{2A\sqrt{I}}{1+B\alpha^0\sqrt{I}} - CI$$

In evaluating the constants 'A' and 'B' the dielectric constant data of Akerlof and Short¹¹, the

TABLE I

Ag, AgCl|HCl(*m*₁)CdCl₂(*m*₂)|H₂,Pt

Mixture of CdCl ₂ and HCl							Temp. = 35°		
[CdCl ₂] _r	[HCl] _r	<i>E</i> in volts	[Cd ⁺⁺] $\times 10^3$	[Cl ⁻] $\times 10^3$	[CdCl ⁺] $\times 10^3$	<i>I</i> $\times 10^3$	<i>K</i> $\times 10^3$	$\log k - \frac{4A\sqrt{I}}{1+B\alpha^0\sqrt{I}}$	
0.003	0.0015	0.50906	1.945	6.445	1.055	8.39	11.88	$\bar{3}.385$	
0.004	0.002	0.49522	2.390	8.390	1.610	10.78	12.45	$\bar{3}.828$	
0.005	0.0025	0.48465	2.732	10.232	2.268	12.96	12.43	$\bar{3}.806$	
0.006	0.003	0.47604	3.030	12.030	2.970	15.06	12.27	$\bar{3}.782$	
0.007	0.0035	0.46873	3.331	13.831	3.669	17.16	12.56	$\bar{3}.776$	
0.008	0.004	0.46248	3.555	15.555	4.445	19.11	12.44	$\bar{3}.758$	
0.009	0.0045	0.45701	3.731	17.231	5.261	20.96	12.20	$\bar{3}.736$	
Temp 40°									
0.003	0.0015	0.51011	1.924	6.424	1.076	8.35	11.49	$\bar{3}.817$	
0.004	0.002	0.49612	2.330	8.330	1.670	10.66	11.62	$\bar{3}.796$	
0.005	0.0025	0.48532	2.700	10.200	2.300	12.90	11.97	$\bar{3}.786$	
0.006	0.003	0.47660	2.980	11.980	3.020	14.96	11.82	$\bar{3}.763$	
0.007	0.0035	0.46931	3.186	13.686	3.814	16.87	11.43	$\bar{3}.733$	
0.008	0.004	0.46290	3.485	15.485	4.515	18.97	11.95	$\bar{3}.736$	
0.009	0.0045	0.45727	3.656	17.156	5.344	20.81	11.74	$\bar{3}.716$	
Temp. 45°									
0.003	0.0015	0.51094	1.901	6.401	1.099	8.30	11.07	$\bar{3}.798$	
0.004	0.002	0.49660	2.330	8.330	1.670	10.66	11.62	$\bar{3}.792$	
0.005	0.0025	0.48581	2.636	10.136	2.364	12.77	11.30	$\bar{3}.758$	
0.006	0.003	0.47689	2.953	11.953	3.047	14.91	11.58	$\bar{3}.750$	
0.007	0.0035	0.46945	3.174	13.674	3.826	16.85	11.34	$\bar{3}.725$	
0.008	0.004	0.46290	3.458	15.458	4.542	18.92	11.77	$\bar{3}.726$	
0.009	0.0045	0.45731	3.573	17.073	5.427	20.65	11.24	$\bar{3}.693$	

viscosity data from our own measurement and the value of 5A° for 'a°' have been used.

Assuming the 1st stage of dissociation of CdCl₂ to be complete, for the species CdCl⁺ ⇌ Cd⁺⁺ + Cl⁻.

$$K = \frac{[Cd^{++}][Cl^-]}{[CdCl^+]} \times \frac{f_{Ca^{++}} f_{Cl^-}}{f_{CdCl^+}}$$

The concentration of each species and the activity co-efficient have been determined in the manner as have been done by Sahu and Prasad⁵.

The results were recorded in the Table 1 for the temperature 35°, 40° and 45° respectively and the thermodynamic dissociation constant found from the plot are also given.

The ΔH value for the reaction CdCl⁺ ⇌ Cd⁺⁺ + Cl⁻ has been calculated by plotting log K_{CdCl⁺} against 1/T and it comes to 1300 ± 100 Cals/mole. The data obtained from the measurements using cell (II) as recorded in Table 2 and 3, and were treated in the following manner. If α is the degree of ionisation of CdCl⁺ and 'm' molality of solution and γ is the real activity coefficient, so that for cell (II)

where $k = \frac{2.3026 RT}{F}$, I' the real ionic strength, is

plotted against 'm' would give E₀ when extrapolated to zero molality. The curves so obtained for different temperatures show humps at molalities higher than 0.01 m but however they can be extrapolated at lower concentrations to yield reasonable values of E₀ for the cell (II). To get accurate E₀ value, it is essential to analyse the data on the lines of Harned and Fitzgerald³, as well as the modified method by Amis¹³. If complete ionisation of cadmium chlorided in solution is assumed, the e.m.f. equation can be written as :

$$E = E_0 - \frac{1}{2}k \log 4m^3 \gamma_{\pm}^3 \quad \dots (2)$$

γ_± is the mean stoichiometric activity coefficients. Using the Debye-Hückel-Brönsted equation for activity coefficient, equation (2) can be written as :

$$E + \frac{1}{2}k \log 4m^3 - \frac{3}{2}kAI^{\frac{1}{2}} = E_0 - \frac{3}{2}kC'I = E_0' \quad \dots (3)$$

where 'I' is the stoichiometric ionic strength and

TABLE 2

Molality of CdCl ₂	Hg, Cd (11.8%) CdCl ₂ (m) in 20% dioxane-water mixture, AgCl, Ag.					
	35°		40°		45°	
	EMF in volts	(Stoichiometric)	EMF in volts	(Stoichiometric)	EMF in volts	(Stoichiometric)
0.002	0.7867	0.6785	0.7868	0.6454	0.7851	0.6454
0.005	0.7615	0.5106	0.7608	0.4955	0.7590	0.4967
0.006	0.7561	0.4873	0.7562	0.4634	0.7551	0.4564
0.007	0.7527	0.4548	0.7536	0.4240	0.7505	0.4391
0.008	0.7494	0.4323	0.7496	0.4102	0.7480	0.4092
0.009	0.7468	0.4103	0.7472	0.3873	0.7455	0.3873
0.010	0.7459	0.3777	0.7452	0.3664	0.7431	0.3701
0.020	0.7298	0.2828	0.7286	0.2778	0.7287	0.2656
0.030	0.7205	0.2381	0.7215	0.2214	0.7197	0.2219
0.040	0.7140	0.2101	0.7144	0.1984	0.7135	0.1944

$$E = E_0 - 2.3026 \frac{RT}{2F} \log \{\alpha(1+\alpha)^2 m^3 \gamma_{\pm}^3\} \quad \dots (1)$$

Using the value of K_{CdCl⁺} obtained from the measurements in the cell (I) an accurate value of α can be calculated for each concentration. It is found that if the Bjerrum Equation¹² is used to obtain a tentative value of 'K_{CdCl⁺}' which when subsequently used to calculate α for each concentration it leads to erroneous results in the value of 'K_{CdCl⁺}' as well as the estimation of the value of E₀. Therefore, it is essential that in using cells of the type (II) the 'K' for the partial ionised electrolyte should be determined by independent methods as the authors have done by using the cell (I). The equation (I) leads to an extrapolation function,

$$E + \frac{1}{2}k \log \{\alpha(1+\alpha)^2 m^3\} - \frac{3}{2}k \left\{ \frac{A | Z_+ Z_- | I^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 + a^0 B I^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right\}$$

'A' is a constant. Using equation (1) for E - E₀ it can be shown that

$$E_0' - E_0 = \frac{1}{2}k \log 4 - \frac{1}{2}k \log \{\alpha(1+\alpha)^2\} -$$

$$-\frac{3}{2}k \log \gamma_{\pm} - \frac{3}{2}kAI^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (4)$$

In order to obtain γ_±' values at different molalities for use in equation (4) the concentration cell without transport (III) was used, the e.m.f. being,

$$E_c = \frac{1}{2}k \log \frac{(a)_h}{(a)_l} \quad \dots (5)$$

(a)_h and (a)_l being the activity of CdCl₂ in higher and lower concentrations. One obtains :

$$\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{k} \left[E_c - \frac{1}{2}k \log \{\alpha(1+\alpha)^2 m^3\}_h + \frac{1}{2}k \log \{\alpha(1+\alpha)^2 m^3\}_l \right] = \log [\gamma_{\pm}(h) / \gamma_{\pm}(l)] \quad \dots (6)$$

The left hand side of the above expression when plotted against ' $m^{\frac{1}{2}}$ ' and extrapolated to zero concentration yield an intercept equal to $-\log \gamma'_{\pm}(l)$ and therefore $\gamma'_{\pm}(h)$ could be calculated. The e.m.f. data for the cell (III) are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Hg,Cd (11.8%)|CdCl (0.005 to 0.04*m*), 20% Dioxane-Water |AgCl|Ag|AgCl|CdCl₂ (0.002*m*), 20% Dioxane-Water |Cd (11.8%) Hg.

Molality of CdCl ₂	EMF in volts		
	35°	40°	45°
0.005	0.0254	0.0256	0.0272
0.006	0.0301	0.0299	0.0313
0.007	0.0336	0.0423	0.0361
0.008	0.0374	0.0364	0.0383
0.009	0.0401	0.0397	0.0411
0.010	0.0410	0.0423	0.0444
0.020	0.0578	0.0578	0.0582
0.030	0.0649	0.0677	0.0674
0.040	0.0723	0.0746	0.0745

The values of E'_0 and using the value of E_0 obtained previously $E'_0 - E_0$ were calculated by using equations (3) and (4) and were plotted against $m^{\frac{1}{2}}$. At all the three temperatures the two plots were found to have close correspondence and were similar to those obtained by Harned and Fitzgerald³. The difference between E'_0 and $E'_0 - E_0$ which gives E_0 were calculated from the graph for as many points as possible and plotted against ' $m^{\frac{1}{2}}$ ' and the plot gives a straight line with zero slope. The process was repeated till a value of E_0 is obtained which did not change with further repetition of the process. The value of E_0 was read off.

The results so calculated out are recorded in Table 4 for four concentrations so also the average values.

The values obtained by the Harned's method and by extrapolation from the graph using equation (2) is also recorded. It is seen that the E_0 value obtained by extrapolation from the graph gives a considerably higher value than either by Harned's method or by Amis's method of calculation.

TABLE 5

Temp.	E_0 in volts.	$-\Delta F_0$ Cal/mole	$-\Delta H_0$ Cal/mole	$-\Delta S_0$ eu.
35°	0.5305	24463		
40°	0.5262	24269	36269	38.3
45°	0.5218	24011	40594	52.1

In the Table 5 the standard free energy change ΔF_0 , enthalpy ΔH_0 and entropy ΔS_0 are given. The standard free energy change for the cell process increases (becomes continually less negative) as the temperature increases. This may be due to among other factors, to the difference in nature and the extent of solvation and increased energy necessary to prevent association of the ions. The reaction is exothermic as indicated by the ΔH_0 value which increases negatively with increase of temperature. The stoichiometric activity coefficient γ_{\pm} for different molalities have been calculated and are given in the Table 3. There is a general trend showing a gradual decrease of γ_{\pm} with increase of concentration as is

TABLE 4

Hg, Cd (11.8%)|CdCl₂(*m*) 20% dioxane-water|AgCl, Ag.

35°		40°		45°	
$K_{CdCl_2} = 7.9 \times 10^3$		$K_{CdCl_2} = 7.76 \times 10^3$		$K_{CdCl_2} = 7.41 \times 10^3$	
Molality of CdCl ₂	E_0 in volts	Molality of CdCl ₂	E_0 in volts	Molality of CdCl ₂	E_0 in volts
0.006	0.5305	0.006	0.5263	0.005	0.5205
0.007	0.5305	0.007	0.5262	0.008	0.5204
0.008	0.5304	0.008	0.5262	0.009	0.5205
0.009	0.5304	0.009	0.5262	0.010	0.5204
Average value of					
E_0 (Amis)	0.5305		0.5262		0.5205
E_0 (Harned)	0.5311		0.5264		0.5208
E_0 (extrapolated)	0.5419		0.5400		0.5385

Amis¹³ in his measurements of CdCl₂ solution in alcohols and alcoholic mixture solutions using cells of the type similar to cell(II) has adopted two changes in the calculation, namely (i) $\gamma_{Cd^{++}} = (\gamma_{CdCl_2})^{\frac{1}{2}}$, (ii) the curve corresponding to the equations for E'_0 and $E'_0 - E_0$ are not considered separately but their differences were computed so that

$$E_0 = E + \frac{3}{2} k \log m + \frac{3}{2} k \log \gamma_{Cd^{++}} -$$

$$-\frac{3}{2} \sqrt{3} . A k \sqrt{m} + \frac{3}{2} k A I^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2} k \log \alpha(1 + \alpha)^2 \quad \dots (7)$$

expected. However the data can not be taken to be absolutely correct above 0.01 (*M*) as our measurement may be taken to hold good below 0.01 (*M*) because the E_0 values calculated at higher concentration show a wide variation from the values reported.

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